

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2021-22 academic year for BPT

DIET AND NUTRITION

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

**Value Added Course
DIET & NUTRITION
for BPT students**

Course duration: 30 hours

Course Objectives

- To provide students with the knowledge of basic terminology of nutrition & the functions of food in healthy life sustenance.
- To impart knowledge about the food classification & role of special functional food.
- To equip students with knowledge and understanding of modern aspects of nutritional science.

VENUE
Srinivas University city
campus, Pandeshwar,
Mangaluru

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Course period	From October till January 2021, during 3 rd semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 2 nd year undergraduates (2020 batch)

Course Description:

The course aims at developing basic understanding about nutrition, its effect on human health and newer advances in food technology. This course encompasses physiological, biochemical and social aspects of food and discusses relationship between metabolites and

human health. The knowledge of nutrition under extreme climate conditions, space nutrition, and sports nutrition empowers students' knowledge and skills to utilize food as a powerful tool for physical, mental, and social wellbeing.

Course Aims:

The course is aimed to enable students to gain knowledge about interaction between food, body and health under normal and special circumstances.

Course Objectives:

- To provide students with the knowledge of basic terminology and several aspects of nutrition and the functions of food in healthy life sustenance;
- To impart knowledge about the food classification, nutrition during special conditions and role of special functional food;
- To equip students with knowledge and understanding of modern aspects of nutritional science and novel food usage.

Course Outcomes:

A successful completion of this course will enable students to:

- ✓ Summarize and critically discuss/ understand both fundamental and applied aspects of food science. They will be able to explain functions of specific nutrients in maintaining health, identifying nutrient specific foods and apply principles from the various facets of food science and related disciplines to solve practical as well as real-world problems.
- ✓ Use current information technologies to locate and apply evidence-based guidelines and protocols and get imparted with critical thinking to take leadership roles in fields of health, dietetics, special nutritional needs and nutritional counseling.

Course Outline:

Week	Lectures	Assignments	Hour ¹
Module 1 «Basics of Food Science»			
1-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic definition, function, classification and dietary sources of foods, nutrition and dietetics. • Concept of malnutrition, health, immunity by food and functions of food. • Classification of macronutrients and micronutrients • Is water a nutrient? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-Study ✓ Home Assignments 	10
Module 2 «Effect of nutraceuticals on health»			

6-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to chemistry of prebiotics and probiotics as functional foods • Effect of nutraceuticals on health and prevention of diseases • Beneficiary microbes and their metabolism for improving health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-Study ✓ Home Assignments 	10
Module 3 «Nutrition during extremes and novel foods»			
11-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutritional principles of adaptation during special circumstances of weather, professions and diseases • Nutrition for high physical work • Sports nutrition • Introduction to novel foods, functional foods and organic foods • Beneficial and harmful effects of genetically modified food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Home Assignments ✓ To devise a food plan for a female athlete who is into track events. ✓ To devise a food plan for a 32 year old male who is into body building 	10

¹ Hours designed for Classroom sessions, video tutorials, Home Assignments, Activities etc.

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

Book References:

1. Maureen Zimmerman and Beth. An introduction to nutrition. Vol. 1
2. Nutrition and Dietetics by Sheila John, Sadhana Rajmohan, S. Karthiga, B.S Vasanthi
3. Jim Mann, A. Stewart Truswell. Essentials of Human Nutriti

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Certificate of Completion

presented to

A MOHAMMAD ADHIL

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

October to January 2021

Total Hours- 30

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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CHRISTO KURIAKOSE

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Handwritten signature of Dr. Sanya A in blue ink.

Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

MOMIN ANUSHA MOHD MUSLIM

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

October to January 2021

Total Hours- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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MUHAMMED SAIDALI S

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"Diet and Nutrition"

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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NAVYA DAMODHARAN

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Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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NISAAMUDEEN T K

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Course Instructor**

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PARAB ANAGHA GOPAL

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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Course Instructor**

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POOJARY KAVYA CHANDRA

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RAICHURI AMAANAHMED ABDUL REHMAN

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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RAKSHA

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Course Instructor

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RICHARD JOBY

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Course Instructor**

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SAFOORA BEEVI M

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Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

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Dr. S. Rajasekar
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SUJAYASHREE

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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SUNAINA

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October to January 2021

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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Certificate of Completion

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SURAJ M NAREGAL

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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SUSHANT GAJANAN MOGER

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Dr. Sanya A
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Dr. S. Rajasekar
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SUSHMITHA S KOTIAN

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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SWEJAL SAKHARAM GAWAS

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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Certificate of Completion

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SYCRATE JOSEPH

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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Certificate of Completion

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TESSA SUSAN JOY

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THARANGINI

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VILANILATH THOMAS BENN SAM

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VISHNU PRIYA P

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VISHWAKARMA SHRADDHA YOGESH

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Course Instructor**

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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VIYUHA MURINGATHARA CHERIAN

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